

SINGLE AND REPEATED IMPACT TESTS ON FIBER COMPOSITE LAMINATES: DAMAGE INDEX vs. RESIDUAL FLEXURAL PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY

In the paper, residual flexural properties of laminates subject to single and repeated impacts are determined. The study is part of a broader investigation on impact characteristics of laminates, which led to the definition of a new damage variable (Damage Index). The correlation between residual properties and the Damage Index is discussed.

Keywords: Damage Progression, Residual Properties, Damage Tolerance, Composite Laminates.

INTRODUCTION

It is generally acknowledged that laminated composite structures are more susceptible to impact damage than metallic structures [1]. In composite structures, impact loading creates internal damage that, even if often not detectable by visual inspection, can cause severe reduction in the laminate strength and stiffness.

The effect of the damage on the mechanical properties, often called damage tolerance, is generally assessed through experimental determination of the residual mechanical properties of the damaged laminates. Compression After Impact tests as well as residual flexural tests are among the test procedures generally adopted.

Damage variables have also been proposed to evaluate the level of damage induced by impact loading directly from parameters acquired during the impact event. Among these variables is the Damage Index DI, introduced by the Authors [2] to monitor damage progression in single and repeated impact tests.

Very briefly, the DI is defined in (1) as:

$$DI = \frac{E_a}{E_i} \frac{s_{MAX}}{s_{QS}} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where the energy ratio is between the absorbed energy E_a and the impact energy E_i , while the displacement ratio is between the maximum dart displacement s_{MAX} registered during the test and the maximum dart displacement s_{QS} measured during a quasi-static

perforation test. For any detail on the DI definition, the reader is referred to reference [2].

At laminate penetration, the impact energy reaches the penetration threshold P_n and the energy ratio saturates to one. However, by taking into account the dart displacement, the DI proved effective in monitoring the range of the penetration process [3] as the DI saturates to one only when the impact energy reaches the perforation threshold P_r , with the dart completely perforating the laminate. In any case penetration is signalled by an abrupt rise of the DI with respect to the initial linear relationship with E_i (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Illustrative example of DI vs. impact energy plot. Initial linear relation and range of penetration process.

When applied to repeated impact tests [4-5], the DI allows for distinguishing between an initial steady phase of damage progression, for which the DI increases linearly with the impact number, and the onset of severe damage mechanisms that lead to laminate perforation in a few impacts (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Illustrative example of DI vs. impact number plot. Steady and unsteady phase of damage progression.

Microscopic observation of impacted specimens [6] showed that evolution of the DI in the steady phase well correlates with the damage accumulation process; in particular, the onset of the unsteady phase was found to correspond to through-thickness transverse cracking in specimen cross-sections.

Level of damage accumulation may therefore be evaluated through DI data points and trends; as a next step, in this paper first results are provided to assess possible use of the DI as an indicator of residual properties. In particular, residual flexural strength and modulus are investigated.

Experimental

Experimental impact tests were performed according to ASTM D5628 standard [7] using an instrumented free-fall drop dart testing machine. The impactor has a total mass of 20kg; its head is hemispherical with a radius of 10mm. Square specimen panels, with 100mm edge, were clamped with a 76.2mm inner diameter, and fixed to a rigid base to prevent slippage of the specimen.

By means of a piezoelectric load cell, force-time curves were acquired and, with a double integration, force-displacement curves were obtained. By additional integration, deformation energy-displacement curves were plotted. Initial conditions were given with the time axis having its origin at the time of impact. The impact velocity was also measured by an optoelectronic device. For further details on the experimental setup, the reader is referred to reference [2].

To determine the post-impact flexural properties of specimens, four-point bending tests were performed according to ASTM D6272 standard [8] using an electro-mechanical testing machine. A support span to depth ratio of 16:1 and a support span to load span ratio of 2:1 were selected according to the standard. This resulted in specimen plane dimensions of 100mm x 50mm. The 50mm width was obtained by cutting off the two sides of the square specimens after impact.

Thickness of the samples varies depending on the laminate type, as shown in Table 1, which reports main characteristics of the laminates used in the study. The crosshead speed was determined according to the standard at 1.9mm/min for the 4.50mm laminates and at 1.7mm/min for the 4.00mm laminates.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the laminates analyzed in the article.

<i>Fiber /Matrix</i>	<i>Lay-up</i>	<i>Thickness [mm]</i>	<i>Acronym used</i>
Glass/Epoxy	[0/90] ₁₅	4.00	GE90s_4.00
	[0 ₃ /90 ₃] ₅	4.00	GE90m_4.00
Glass/Epoxy	[random/-45/+45/0 ₂] ₂	4.50	GE45_4.50

Bending of post-impact specimens was undertaken with the impacted surface experiencing compression and the back-face undergoing tension. Four-point bending was preferred over three-point bending to avoid load application at the location of greatest impact damage.

Load-displacement curves were acquired during the flexural tests and the maximum load F_{max} as well as the slope of the tangent to the initial straight-line m were determined (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Illustrative example of load vs. displacement plot. Evaluation of the slope of the tangent to the initial straight-line m and of the maximum load F_{max} .

The flexural strength S was then computed from the maximum load according to the well known equation (2), as given in ASTM D6272:

$$S = \frac{3 F_{max} \cdot L}{4 b \cdot t^2}, \quad (2)$$

where L is the support span, b and t the width and the thickness of the beam, respectively.

Similarly, the tangent modulus of elasticity E_b was computed from equation (3):

$$E_b = 0.17m \frac{L^3}{b \cdot t^3}, \quad (3)$$

A minimum of 2 specimens was tested for each material under each testing condition. Test conditions in terms of impact energy and number of impacts are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Impact test conditions prior to residual properties measurement.

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Impact Energy [J]</i>	<i>Number of impacts</i>
GE45_4.50	[6,12,18,25,49,74,86,92]	1
GE90s_4.00	49	[1,3,5]
GE90m_4.00	49	[1,3,5,8]

TEST RESULTS

Residual flexural strength and modulus of elasticity are plotted in Figure 4 as a function of impact energy. As already reported in the literature [9-11], the general trend of property degradation is similar for strength and modulus. A power function was found to well fit the experimental data.

Owing to the linear relationship between the DI and the impact energy up to the penetration threshold (Figure 5), a power function between the DI and the residual properties can be found (Figure 6).

Figure 4: Residual flexural properties as a function of the impact energy. (a) Residual flexural strength. (b) Residual modulus of elasticity. GE45_4.50.

Figure 5: DI vs. impact energy plot up to the penetration threshold. GE45_4.50.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: Residual flexural properties as a function of DI. (a) Residual flexural strength. (b) Residual modulus of elasticity. GE45_4.50.

Figure 6 shows that the correlation coefficients for both the residual strength and the residual modulus of elasticity are about the same when plotted against the impact energy or the DI. However, an advantage of the DI over the impact energy is visible in Figure 1: the abrupt rise of the DI prior to penetration allows taking into account the significant drop of residual properties reported in the literature [12] for impact energies approaching the penetration threshold.

When considering the case of repeated impact tests, the literature devoted to the evaluation of residual properties appears very limited [13-15]. Generally, it is recognized that residual strength falls rapidly with increasing number of impacts to then level off; however it should be noted that in all literature sources impact tests never approach final perforation.

Similarly to what found for the single impact case, the trend of the DI with the number of impacts (Figure 2) allows plotting the residual properties against the damage variable and possibly distinguishing between an initial phase of steady damage accumulation and a final phase before perforation. In this last unsteady phase, material properties are indeed expected to drop abruptly.

Figure 7 reports the DI values of GE90s_4.00 and GE90m_4.00 specimens tested at different number of impacts (Table 2), up to the onset of the unsteady phase of damage accumulation (linear variation of the DI with the number of impacts).

Typical load-displacement curves of the residual flexural tests are reported in Figure 8 for different number of impacts. Residual flexural strength and residual modulus of elasticity are then plotted in Figure 9 as a function of the DI.

Figure 7: DI vs. impact number plot up to the onset of the unsteady phase. Impact Energy 49J. GE90s_4.00 and GE90m_4.00.

Figure 8: Load displacement curves of residual flexural tests for different number of impacts. Impact Energy 49J. GE90m_4.00.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9: Residual flexural properties as a function of DI. (a) Residual flexural strength. (b) Residual modulus of elasticity. GE90s_4.00 and GE90m_4.00.

Similarly to the single impact case, a power function is found to well fit the relationship between the DI and the two residual properties. In this case the exponent of the power function is close to one and indeed a linear regression can also be used with only a slight reduction in the correlation coefficient. However, it should be noted that range of variation of the DI is more limited when compared to the single impact example.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In the paper, residual flexural properties of laminates subject to single and repeated impacts are determined. The study is part of a broader investigation on impact characteristics of laminates, which led to definition of a new damage variable (DI). Previous studies have shown that the DI may give a qualitative indication of the level of damage accumulation within the laminate after single or repeated impact tests.

In this work, a first step was moved in the direction of assessing that this macroscopic damage variable well correlates with quantitative characteristics like residual flexural properties.

In particular, when compared against the impact energy the discontinuous trend of the DI allows describing through a single power function the 'steady phase' of damage progression as well as the significant drop of residual properties when perforation is approached. This is true for both single and repeated impact tests.

Further experimental tests are needed to test the validity of the approach against other materials and to investigate whether a master curve exists that can relate residual properties normalized by stiffness and strength properties of undamaged laminates to DI values.

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